

Historical Development of Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo (1980 - 2009): (First Teacher's Training Institution in Nigeria)

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Abstract

The paper examined the historical development of Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo, Nigeria: the first teacher's training institution St. Andrew's College Oyo (1896) and subsequently upgraded to the college of education (1980). The paper traced the origin of college. Historical research design which relying on primary and secondary sources of information was adopted. The variables considered in this paper included the origin, objectives, milestones, staffing, students' enrolments, facilities in place and impact of the college on the host communities. Findings obtained confirmed that the college has succeeded in producing teachers for basic education programme thus fulfilling the national objectives of producing teachers and the required manpower for primary and lower level of secondary education in Nigeria. The staffing, students' enrolments and the infrastructural facilities of the college have improved; and that the college is financed by Oyo State Government and tefund. The alumni of the college had contributed immensely to their school. The college had impacted positively on its host communities. Based on the discussions of this paper, it was recommended that additional infrastructural facilities be provided by the State Government and other stakeholders in teacher education.

Keywords: Historical, Development, Emmanuel Alayande College of Education and Teacher's Training Institution.

Introduction

The National Policy on Education, specifically on teacher education (FGN, 1998 and 2004) stated the goals of teacher education as the production of highly motivated conscientious and efficient classroom teachers. Nigerian Colleges of Education emerged from the implementation of Ashby Commission Report of 1960, which recommends that Advanced Teachers' Colleges (ATCs) be established which was renamed Nigeria College of Education to produce holders of the Nigeria Certificate in Education, a non-degree but highly qualitative Professional Certificate in Education (Ashby, 1960, Banjo 1961, and Adeyinka, 1990).

It is important to note that the two reports emphasised the need to train Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) graduates also to be able to teach in Nigerian primary schools. Olayanju (2013) recorded that the views of Ashby (1960) and Banjo Commissions fell in line with, and were shared by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1998) where it was clearly stated that NCE will ultimately become the minimum basic qualification for entry into the teaching profession.

Taiwo (1980), Adeyinka (1996) and Osokoya (2002) recalled that the creation of more states in Nigeria in 1976 and introduction of the Universal Primary Education in the same year (1976) had some positive impact on the growth of Colleges of Education. Therefore, more colleges of education were established in the country immediately after 1976. By 2009, the number of these colleges had risen to 85 (NCCE, 2009) with 21 Federal, 43 State and 21 Private Colleges of Education as reflected in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Trend in the Development of Colleges of Education in Nigeria as at 2009.

S/N	Types of Colleges of Education	Number Established
1.	Federal Colleges of Education	21
2.	States Colleges of Education	43
3.	Privately Owned Colleges	21
	Total	85

Source: Olayanju (2013)

This paper therefore aimed at answering the following questions:

1. How did Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo Nigeria originates? Specify some important milestones of the college between 1980 and 2009.
2. Why the college was established and the extent to which these objectives been met between 1980 and 2009?
3. What were the trends in the curriculum development, student enrolment and staffing in the college between 1980 and 2009?
4. What has been the pattern of infrastructural development and funding in the college between 1980 and 2009?
5. In what ways has the impact of the college were felt by its host communities between 1980 and 2009?
6. What were the major challenges facing the college between 1980 and 2009?

Methodology

Historical research method was adopted for this study which depended much on primary and secondary sources for its data especially the documentary analysis through library search, internet, newspapers, relevant textbooks, relevant higher degree thesis and the records from the registry and the establishment unit of the college and the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) memo over the years. The instruments used were questionnaire and oral interview with Alabi (2011) and Ogundare (2011).

Theoretical Framework

Systems Theory

This study is anchored on the systems theory, system theory rests on the facts that each of the component parts performs specific functions for the survival of the whole. Each part interacts with and is interdependent of the other parts and other systems, which constitute the environment (Fabunmi, 2002). Most systems are further divided into sub-systems, for example, the education system can be sub-divided to primary, secondary and tertiary education (of which Colleges of Education is a sub – system).

These processing activities enable the system to yield outputs which can fulfill the system's aspirations and expectations. These outputs consist of all changes that the school system has produced: the products of the system. The outputs (students) flow across the boundary to the larger society, where the inputs were drawn to form a dynamic organic whole.

System Model

Channel for Trends of Transformation /Development

Fig. 1: Trends of Transformation /Development of Colleges of Education.

Source: Fabunmi (2002) adapted by Olayanju (2009).

Justification for using the Systems Theory

The justification for using this theory is premised on the fact that college of Education as [the whole] that is, an institution of learning is made up the students, staff – academic and administrative, physical structures, facilities and equipment, funding, curriculum, time- table, assessment and supervision [parts]. Therefore, college of education system is cyclic in nature, being an open system, just like other social organisations. It absorbs its inputs from the environment and discharges outputs to the environment.

College of Education system maintains close relationship with its environment. For it to survive, continuous and adequate inputs have to be supplied. Each of the inputs (educational facilities, students, curriculum, financial, and human resources) is related to colleges' performance and system's efficiency. Quality of the outputs depends greatly on the nature (quality and quantity) of the inputs and also the effectiveness of the transformation process. Both the transformation process and the output will be defective if the input is inadequate, poor or unavailable.

Origin of Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo (1980-2009)

Oyo State College of Education, Oyo, formerly known as St. Andrew's College of Education, Oyo which was described as the Pacesetter in Education. This description is very apt taking into consideration the leading role of the institution (The St Andrew's College) in teacher education in the Country (Solaru, 1964, Olukoju, 2001, and Fafunwa, 1991).

The government of Late Chief Bola Ige of Oyo State during the second republic upgraded the St. Andrew's College, Oyo, to a campus of the then Oyo State College of Education, Ilesa, with effect from September, 1980. By October 2, 1980, 224 NCE students had resumed in the College. St. Andrew's College was a campus of the then Oyo State College of Education, Ilesa (1980-1983), and Ila-Orangun (1983-1985) as an affiliated institution. October 1985, after the rationalisation of the seven Colleges of Education of the erstwhile Oyo State into three, St. Andrew's College became an autonomous College of Education. With the political re-arrangement of the country on the 27th August 1991, St. Andrew's College of Education

(SACOED) emerged as the only College of Education in the present Oyo State (Ukeje, 1996, Osokoya, 2008 and Adeyinka 2005).

In September, 2001, the State Government formally approved the Oyo State College of Education, Oyo (OYSCOED) as the new name of the college from the formal St. Andrew's College. Subsequently, a law titled "Oyo State College of Education Law, 2004" was promulgated in July, 2005. The institution's name was later changed to Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo in 2006. In the past twenty-five years of existence as a college, there had been one Head of Campus, one Principal and four Provosts. Their names and year of administration are stated below:

The Past Head of Campus, Principal, Acting Provost and Provosts of the College were:

1. Dr. S.A. Gesinde - Head of Campus, Oct. 1980-30th Nov. 1981
2. Dr. A.O. Afolayan – Principal, 1st Dec. 1981-30th Sept. 1985
3. Dr. Tunji Oladapo - Acting Provost, 1st Oct. 1985-30th Dec. 1987
4. Dr. Tunji Oladapo – Provost, 1st Jan. 1987-31st Dec 30. 1991
5. Mr. J.A. Adesiyani - Acting Provost, 31st Dec. 1991-31st Dec. 1992
6. Prof. Olajire Olaniran – Provost, 1st Jan. 1993-31st Dec. 1999
7. Dr. Adekunle Ladipo Ogunmola - Acting Provost, 1st Jan. 2000-20th June. 2000 and as substantive Provost, from 21st June. 2000 to June 2008
9. Dr. Alabi, Amos Oyetunde – Provost, June, 2008 – up to the time of this study in 2009.

Important Landmarks in the College Development

1896 - Proper recognition as St. Andrew's College, Oyo as a Teachers' Grade II College

September, 1980 – Campus of the then Oyo State College of Education, Ilesa.

1983 - Campus of the then Oyo State College of Education, Ila-Orangun

1987 - Autonomous College of Education, St Andrew's College of Education Edict No. 11 of 1986.

1988 – The college started a part-time NCE (Primary) Sandwich Programme during the 1988/89 session.

Three study centres were initially created namely: Oyo, Iseyin and Ogbomosho.

1991 – As the only College of Education in Oyo State following the creation of Osun State from former Oyo State.

1997 - Degree Awarding Status: The College started a degree programme in Education in affiliation with the University of Ado-Ekiti (UNAD) and this has been on till date.

- Wed, April 29, 1998 – the 14th and 15th Convocation Ceremony in the College, Oyo for the Award of the Nigeria Certificate in Education for the 1995/1996 and 1996/1977 sets of graduants of the College.
- July 27, 2000 - During the 16th and 17th Graduation Ceremony of the College, the Executive Governor of Oyo State, Alhaji Lam Onaolapo Adesina disclosed that the state government has agreed to hand-over the premises of the then St. Andrews College of Education to its owner, the Anglican Communism.
- June 1, 2001 – Handed over the premises of the College to Anglican Church in preparation for the establishment of Anglican Private University, later known as Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo
- June, 2001 - The Executive Governor of Oyo State, Alhaji Lam Adesina, has formally chnaged the name of the College be changed from St. Andrews College of Education to Oyo State College of Education, and the governor pronounced relocation of the college to a virgin land at Erelu to accommodate the new college that vacate the former campus of St. Andrew’s College to her original owner and proprietor, the Anglican Church of Nigeria.
- September 20, 2001 - The Oyo State Commissioner for Education, Science and Technology, Dr. Amballyu Moronkola Thomas, paid a one-day visit to the college. During his visit, he commissioned five (5) completed projects on both the main and Isokun Campuses.
- September, 2001 – The students of the college received a bus gift from the Oyo State Government.
- September 20, 2001- The Oyo State Honourable Commissioner for Education, Science and Technology, Dr. Ambaliyu Moronkola Thomas commended the working team spirit exhibited by members of the management team of the college. This commendation was made during this visit to the college on September 20, 2001.
- 2001 - Successful launching of ₦500 Million Endowment fund Launch
- April 8-12, 2002 - NCCE holds workshop: a National workshop was held on the final review of the National Commission for Colleges of Education Minimum Academic Standards between April 8-12, 2002 in the college.
- May 11, 2002 - The College recorded another milestone as the Executive Gov. of Oyo State Alh. Lam Adesina commissioned the College cybercafé.
- Thursday April 10, 2003 - Lanlate Satellite Campus of the Oyo State College of Education, Oyo, held its 1st Matriculation ceremony for 2002/2003 session.

- June 3, 2003 - Best Provost Award in Nigeria awarded by the Senior Staff Union of Colleges of Education in Nigeria (SSUCOEN) to Dr. A. L. Ogunmola
- June, 2003 - OYSCOED College Venture registered with corporate Affairs Commission June 12, 2003.
- 2004 - Oyo State Government Law 2004' thus abolishing 'the St. Andrew's College of Education Edict No. 11 of 1986 and replaced with Oyo State College of Education, Oyo
- May 14, 2004, Friday - 24 Students of the institution were presented with the Federal Government Scholarship Award on Friday 14, 2004.
- May 27, 2004 - The College inaugurated parents' forum.
- June 22, 2004 - Release of the sum of ₦187.5 million for the construction of the 200 phase of the physical facilities at the college by the Oyo State Government.
- Feb. 10, 2005 - Matriculation ceremony of 1682 students in the regular NCE programme, and 1, 500 in the sandwich NCE Programme.
- Thursday June 23 & 24 2005 - NUC Accreditation team visited the College, Dr. M.A.G. Akale, NCCE Director of Programmes and leader of Accreditation team paid a visit to the college in 2005.
- OYSCOED appreciated Governor Lam Adesina - Prof. Oyedeji also used the forum to express appreciation to the State Governor under the able leadership of Governor Lam Adesina for his commitment to the provision of qualitative education which was evidenced by his commitment to the prompt release of fund from loan granted to boost the College performance and thereby increasing the Internally Generated Revenue (IGR) for the College.
- February 14 and 15, 2006 - NCCE Council members visited OYSCOED: it was led by Alhaji AbdulWaheed Ibrahim.
- May 3, 2006 - Dr. David Olusoji Adejumo appointed the Chairman of the Governing Council of college by the Executive Governor, Otunba (Dr.) Christopher Adebayo Alao Akala.
- May 25, 2006 - 20th, 21st, 22nd, 23rd Convocation Graduation Ceremony combined a four- event in one. The graduates of that day were the first set of graduands under the new name of OYSCOED. The occasion also marked the 25 years of the existence of the college.
- August 14, 2006 - Dr. (Mrs.) Ogunwuyi, Adeola Olufunmilayo became the first female dean in the College (The Dean, School of Education)

April 9, 2008 - The College sensitisation workshop on Degree Awarding status for the college was organised at the College conference Hall, Erelu, on Wednesday, April 9, 2008. It was anchored by Prof. Yoloye, former Director of Institute of Education, and University of Ibadan.

2008 Re-accreditation exercise of the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE). The College recently got an accreditation approval from the NCCE. The team was led by Alhaji Aliyu Sanni Mohammed. The team commended the college management for the development of the school adding that the college has the teaching and infrastructure facilities alongside human resources to become a degree awarding institution in education.

2008 – The college got a donation of ten (10) sets of computers recently from Union Bank Plc. as part of its corporate social responsibility.

2008 - A bus donation was presented to the College by a director of the First Bank, Prince Ajibola Afonja.

Objectives for Establishing the College

The college was established with the primary aim of training teachers for the primary and junior secondary levels of education in Nigeria.

The objectives of the college like all other Federal and State Colleges of Education in Nigeria are listed below:

- (a) To produce highly motivated, conscientious and efficient classroom teachers for all levels of our educational system;
- (b) To encourage a spirit of enquiry and creativity in teachers;
- (c) To integrate teachers fit into the social life of the community and society at large and to enhance their commitments to the national goals;
- (d) To provide teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate for their assignments; and make them adaptable to every situation.
- (e) To enhance teachers' commitments to the teaching profession.

Training teachers for Nigeria's primary and junior secondary schools was the college's main goal when it was founded.

This is in line with the National Policy on Teacher Education (1981. p.38, 1998 and 2004) where it has been stated:

Teacher Education shall be given a major emphasis in all our educational planning, because no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers. Teachers will be regularly updated with innovations for nurturing excellence in their profession. Government will introduce measures to enable teachers to participate more in the production and assessment of educational materials and teaching aids, planning and development of curriculum ... innovations and new techniques (National Policy on Education, 2004).

The extent to which the objectives for establishing the college has been met and its contribution to the development of teaching professional in the state between 1980 and 2009 were realised. One of the objectives of the college is the production of teachers to teach in the various programmes of elementary and Basic Education and the mandate to train teachers for this level of education in the country. To this end, Colleges of Education are better suited to produce teachers for the current Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme (Tahir, 2003).

Furthermore, these colleges strived in ensuring that the teachers produced were of good quality and were able to handle different instruction situations, whether in literacy, special education and vocational centres or the elementary levels of primary education.

Findings from the paper also revealed that the college to some extent is endowed with competent teachers and adequate facilities in promoting a conducive atmosphere for teaching and learning and that the burden of steady supply of the required teachers for Universal Basic Education programme in Nigeria hinges on colleges of education. Moreover, these colleges were up to the task in their quest of preparation and production of teachers for providing basic literacy, numeracy and initial learning skills in Early Childhood Care Education, and Basic Education as reported in a study by Olayanju (2006).

As part of the ways of producing teachers for every segment of elementary and Upper Basic levels of education, the colleges in conjunction with the National Teachers' Institute (NTI) organizes and runs in-service teacher education programme. This is done in bid to augment the shortage of teachers produced by regular NCE programmes to service both primary and junior segment of secondary schools. By doing so, the Colleges of Education are fulfilling one of their basic functions of community service as provided by the various laws establishing them. Colleges of Education had performed creditably well in this respect.

To this end, the colleges were also consistent and proactive in reaching out to the larger society with a variety of in-service short training courses, seminars and workshops for educational managers, inspectors,

supervisors, teachers and instructors, who deal with the day-to-day operations of Universal Basic Education programme at the grassroots level.

To a very large extent, the college had contributed immensely to engender conducive learning environment and eradicate illiteracy in Nigeria through its efforts of introducing Early Childhood Care Education (ECCE) and expanding facilities for primary education studies in the college in line with the new Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme and Education for All (EFA) initiatives of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (Fafunwa, 2008).

Table 2 below reflects the curricula offerings in the college and other conventional colleges of education in Nigeria.

Table 2: Courses currently offered in Nigeria Colleges of Education

S/N	Arts & Social Sciences	Education	Languages	Sciences	Vocational & Technical Education
1.	Geography	Primary Education Studies	Hausa	Physics	Business Education
2.	Political Science	Curriculum & Instruction	French	Computer Sc.	Agricultural Education
3.	Economics	Educational Foundations	English	Mathematics	Home Economics
4.	Social Studies	Education Psychology	Arabic	Integrated Sc	Fine & Applied Arts.
5.	Christian Religion Studies	General Studies	Igbo	Chemistry	Technical Education
6.	Catechetical Programme – Theology & Education	Early Childhood Care Education (ECCE)	Yoruba	Biology	

7.	Islamic Studies			Physical & Health Education	
8.	History				
9.	Music				
10.	Cultural and Creative Arts				

Source: Student handbook (2009): Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo.

Olayanju (2006) reported that in line with the Philosophy of Nigerian Education as stipulated by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2004) Section 1 and the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, the colleges of education have performed creditably well by ensuring that the provisions of the National Policy on Education specifically on teacher education were achieved.

Staffing

There are human resource needs for administration, management, research and teaching as well as for support and technical staff which calls for an urgent need for capacity building in the college. The “academic and professional competence of teachers is a major determinant of education quality” at all levels of education. As at April 2009, the College has adequate human resources. Table 3 presents a summary of the academic staff list on ground.

Table 3: Distribution of Academic Staff in the college between 1980 and 2009

Year/Session	Number of Academic Staff
2000/2001	184
2001/2002	217
2002/2003	217
2003/2004	249
2004/2005	249
2005/2006	316
2006/2007	330
2007/2008	345

2008/2009	369
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Source: Fieldwork (Olayanju, 2009)

Table 3 above shows the staffing situations of the college across the years; the number of teaching staff increased based on the needs of the colleges. There were variations from school to school as staff strength is often determined by the population of students among other factors. As of April 2009, the College has adequate human resources. Currently, the college has a high number of well-qualified academic staff members.

Admission Process

Initially, all the colleges of education admitted their students based on internally conducted entrance examinations. Later, the process was harmonised and this responsibility was hijacked by the Joint Admission Matriculation and Board (JAMB) and later the Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME).

Student Enrolment

Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo, started operating with the initial enrolments of 224 students in 1980.

Table 4: Emmanuel Alayande College of Education Oyo Students' Enrolment Trend, 2000 – 2009

Year /Session	Students Enrolment Trend
2000/2001	5634
2001/2002	6480
2002/2003	7480
2003/2004	9137
2004/2005	8408
2005/2006	6812
2006/2007	6642
2007/2008	7258
2008/2009	1,2845

Source: Fieldwork (Olayanju, 2009)

Fig. 2: Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo, Students' Enrolment Trend 2000-2009

The student's enrolment trends in the college at the beginning of the 2000/2001 session, was 5,634. In the 2001/2002 session, the students' intakes increased to 6,480 and this continued up to the 2003/2004 session. This increment in students' enrolment was due to the free education policy implemented by Oyo State under the leadership of Governor Lam Adesina between 1999 and 2003. However, the students' enrolment dropped from the beginning of the 2004/2005 session to 8,408 as reflected in Table 4 and Fig. 2 graphically illustrated above.

By 2005/2006 it declined to 6,812 students and later to 6,642 students in the 2006/2007 session. These declines were a result of some political problems occasioned by student riots and industrial actions by the staff of Nigerian tertiary institutions. However, the student's enrolment in the college started increasing in the 2007/2008 session and incidentally rose geometrically to 12,845 in the 2008/2009 session. The college developed quantitatively in terms of admission. This was a result of the commitments of both Governor Rashidi Adewolu Ladoja and Otunba Christopher Adebayo Alao-Akala to education in the State during their tenure.

Physical Development:

Infrastructural Facilities in the College

The college took off from the premises of the defunct Grade II, the St. Andrews' College, located at Oke-Ebo in Oyo town in 1980, and later occupied the premises of the defunct Grade III Local Authority Teachers' College, located at Isokun, also in Oyo town to accommodate both the students and the staff of the new institution.

The development of the College's physical structures has been monumental. The old structures of the St. Andrew's College premises were constantly rehabilitated, while some new structures were put in place between 1980 and 2001. The Anglican Communion of Nigeria, however, requested the use of the premises of St. Andrew's College of Education, Oyo from the Oyo State Government, for the establishment of an Anglican University. So the government formally handed over the premises to the Anglican Communion (former Church Missionaries Society, CMS) in June 2001.

The relocation of the college to its permanent site in Erelu, Oyo has been seen by many to be a blessing in disguise as state-of-the-art infrastructure had been put up to meet the challenges of the time. The permanent site becomes a cynosure of all eyes, as it has been described by various people as a "model" among its peers.

In the case of the college's relocation to the new site from the former St. Andrews College, Oyo, established in 1896, moved to its permanent site at Erelu in Oyo in 2003 was an important landmark.

1. 500 Sitting Capacity Lecture Theaters
2. Fully equipped laboratories (Sciences and Languages)
3. An Agricultural Science Laboratory
4. Fully equipped Computer Laboratory
5. Purchases of Fourteen-seater Buses for Schools
6. 1,200 sitting capacity Alao Akala Large Lecture Theatre through ETF 2008
7. 1,600 sitting capacity Lecture Theatre opposite the School of Languages through ETF 2010 BOT – Special Intervention
8. 500 sitting capacity Lecture Theatre in the School of Science through ETF 2010 BOT – Special Intervention
9. 1,500-capacity e-library with 100 units of computers

10. A Fourteen-seater Bus donated by ETF
11. A Fourteen-seater Bus donated by the First Bank of Nigeria Plc
12. A storey building with 20 offices for lecturers in the School of Education
13. A Cybercafé and ICT centre
14. Home Management Residential Flat for Home Economics Department

Pattern of Funding in the College between 1980 and 2009

Funding plays a very crucial role in the implementation of any development programme. It is imperative to note that the success of any education project hinges on adequate funding; no meaningful developmental programme in education can take place without adequate funding. (ESA, 2007, p.281).

Fafunwa (1974) acknowledged that the financing of education has been a joint responsibility of the Federal, State and Local governments. In the realisation of the college objectives, the institution got its funds especially the monthly allocations/subventions from the Federal Government. In some cases, the Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) assisted the college.

Apart from this, the college also derived its funds from the revenue from school fees, levies from continuing education programmes, consultancy, letting of halls and other charges such as business centres as Internally Generated Revenue (IGR). Another source of funding for the College was provided through TETFund. The fund was made available and expected to be used for the construction of physical structures and infrastructural facilities in the college and the training of staff both local and foreign.

Impact of Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo on the Development of its host communities between 1980 and 2009

The findings of this paper revealed that the College had produced a crop of educated elite. These classes of people are now manning prominent posts in various fields of human endeavour at the state, national and international levels. This is reflected in the lists of the Alumni (Old Students) of the college: Barrister Bosun Oladele – The Current Honourable Commissioner for Information and Orientation, Oyo State; Mrs. Shogo, Bisi – Principal Administrative Officer; Mrs. Ajasa, F. A. – Senior Lecturer, the current Head of Department (H.O.D.) Department of Primary Education Studies; Dr Ayena, Olugbenga Oladapo – The current chairman, COEASU, the college chapter, Mr Ayanwale, Olukunle – Senior Lecturer, the current H.O.D., Department of Social Studies; Bioku Adeyemi Tanko – Student Union President, 1992/1993 (presently, an officer in the Oyo State Ministry of Agriculture); Alh. Aderibigbe, Semiu A – Formerly of the Department of General Studies,

Oyo Doctoral Student, University of London, United Kingdom; Dr. Shittu, John Idowu – Lecturer, Department of Educational Psychology.

Thus, within a period of twenty-nine (29) years i.e. (1980 – 2009) the college has recorded monumental achievements in her educational history in general and teacher education in particular. The establishment of the institution has had a lot of positive impacts on society. And this also confers economic benefits to the towns in which they were located. Such towns enjoyed unhindered access to good road networks to administrative divisions or the state capital. Facilities such as bookshops, Post offices, markets, and banks are usually established. This College of Education had other advantages. Its strategic location served as a growth point for the communities concerned. The college is usually ahead of many homes in the maintenance of high standards of personal hygiene and sanitation general cleanliness, inculcation of the spirit of respect for elders, development of a high sense of humility, good attitude to work, and preparation for leadership and self-dependence. The college also served as the centre of enlightenment and sold the virtues discussed above to its immediate communities.

The findings of this paper also revealed that there were challenges facing institution under review between 1980 and 2009. Inadequate Training in Practical Skills (Internship/Teaching Practice Exercise): The time spent on internship or teaching practice is inadequate. Incidentally, the teaching practice/internship is the only practical aspect of the trainer education programme (the practicum). Teaching practices are supposed to take a full one session of the three-year course.

In addition to the above, some NCE teachers were not Information and Communication Technology (ICT) compliant. Indeed, the success of ICT in the school system depends largely on teachers and their levels of skills in integrating ICT into the teaching process. The teachers of the future need to be trained and retrained in ICT.

Recommendations

Based on the discussions of this paper, the following recommendations were made:

1. It was recommended that additional infrastructural facilities be provided by the Federal Government and other stakeholders in teacher education.
2. The Federal Government should increase budgetary allocation to the college to meet its target in the provision of social welfare services to the college.
3. The College should explore other avenues to improve its internally generated revenue.

4. The Alumni Associations of the institution should rise to the challenges of the upliftment of their alma mater positively.
5. The Oyo State Government should endeavour to upgrade Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo to a full-fledged University of education without affiliation with other Universities.

Conclusion

The findings of this paper revealed that the rationale behind the establishment of Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo, between 1980 and 2009 was to prepare and produce teachers for the primary and junior segments of secondary schools in Nigeria. In addition, the lecturers in this college of education worked under intolerable conditions such as a lack of instructional materials, the absence of a health scheme and several other welfare incentives which their counterparts in the universities enjoyed.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS USED IN THE STUDY

ATCs	-	Advanced Teachers' Colleges
COE	-	Colleges of Education.
NCCE	-	National Commission for Colleges of Education.
NUC	-	National Universities Commission.
NBS	-	National Bureau of Statistics.
NERDC-		Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council
ESA	-	Education Sector Analysis.
UBE	-	Universal Basic Education.
UNESCO	-	United Nations Education and Scientific Organisation.
UNICEF	-	United Nations Children Fund.
FGN	-	Federal Government of Nigeria
FME	-	Federal Ministry of Education.
FRN	-	Federal Republic of Nigeria
SME	-	State Ministry of Education.
MOE	-	Ministry of Education.
NCE	-	Nigeria Certification in Education.
NTI	-	National Teachers' Institute
TTC	-	Teachers Training College.
GRADE I	-	Training Institutions for Grade I Teachers.
GRADE II	-	Training Institutions for Grade II Teachers.
GRADE III	-	Training Institutions for Grade III Teachers.
ETF	-	Education Trust Fund.
TETFUND	-	Tertiary Education Trust Fund
COEASU	-	Colleges of Education Academic Staff Union.
EFA	-	Education for All.
MDGS	-	Millennium Development Goals.
ILO	-	International Labour Organisation.
NGOs	-	Non – Governmental Organisations.

ICT	-	Information and Communication Technology.
FOS	-	Federal Office of Statistics.
BMAS	-	Benchmark Minimum Academic Standard.
SACOED	-	St. Andrew's College of Education
OYSCOED	-	Oyo State College of Education
UNAD	-	University of Ado-Ekiti
SSUCOE	-	Senior Staff Union of Colleges of Education
ECCE	-	Early Childhood Care and Education
JAMB	-	Joint Admission Matriculation Board
UTME	-	Unified Tertiary Matriculation Board
HOD	-	Head of Department
IGR	-	Internally Generated Revenue
BOT	-	Built Operate and Transfer
CMS	-	Church Missionary Society
UBE	-	Universal Basic Education